

References

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CHANGES OF PRO- AND ANTIOXIDANT SYSTEMS IN PATIENTS WITH BRAIN CONCUSSION

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ABSTRACT

The state of pro- and antioxidant systems in patients with brain concussion has been studied. The definite patterns of the functioning of these systems in this pathology have been disclosed.

Keywords: pathogenesis, pro- and antioxidant systems, mild cranial trauma, brain concussion.

Introduction. Mild traumatic brain injury (TBI) is one of the most common types of nervous system lesions. Nearly 80% of all mild TBI cases are presented by brain concussion. Despite the term “mild” this type of trauma is characterized by high frequency of post-traumatic complications. The cause of it should be found in peculiarities of acute period of TBI when a cascade of irreversible changes in neural tissue is formed.

It has been proved that activation of lipid peroxidation and biopolymers is an early universal and extremely sensitive marker of injury. It is characteristic of various pathological conditions including traumatic lesions of nervous system. The complexity of this problem is determined by favorable conditions for the progression of free radical pathology in central nervous system that include high lipid content (optimal substrate for lipid peroxidation), maximum oxygen consumption, well developed system of biological membranes. These facts stipulate particular susceptibility of brain for oxidative injury of cerebral structures. Given

the above we considered it appropriate to assess the extent and dynamics of pro- and antioxidant imbalance in patients with brain concussion.

Materials and methods. We have examined 38 patients with brain concussion aged 18-43 years and the control group which comprised 15 practically healthy individuals comparable by age and sex. Brain concussion was diagnosed based on neurological and instrumental examination. Biochemical studies were done in plasma and erythrocytes of patients and donors. Blood sampling was performed in the morning on an empty stomach on the first, third and fifth day after traumatic injury. It included malonic aldehyde, ceruloplasmin, medium weight molecules, glutathione, HS-groups, catalase activity.

Results and discussion. The degree of activation of free radical processes was assessed by content of malonic aldehyde which is one of the final products of lipid peroxidation. On the first day the level of malonic aldehyde was practically equal to normal ranges. However on the third day and especially on the fifth day we have observed noticeable increase of plasma level of malonic aldehyde by 38.6% (Table 1).

Table 1

The dynamics of pro- and antioxidant systems indexes in patients with brain concussion

	1 st day	3 rd day	5 th day	Control
Malonic aldehyde, $\mu\text{mol/L}$	18,55 \pm 0,38 p<0,05	25,7 \pm 0,6 p<0,05	26,8 \pm 0,46	7,74 \pm 0,28
Ceruloplasmin, mg/L	231,8 \pm 4,2 p<0,05	212,5 \pm 2,7	184,6 \pm 2,9	186,26 \pm 2,3
Catalase activity, $\mu\text{mol/min L}$	38,4 \pm 0,7 p<0,05	25,8 \pm 0,73	12,6 \pm 0,43	11,62 \pm 0,3
Glutathione	0,71 \pm 0,015 p<0,05	0,54 \pm 0,02	0,36 \pm 0,014	0,30 \pm 0,015
SH-groups, $\mu\text{mol/ml}$	2,41 \pm 0,06 p<0,05	1,9 \pm 0,03	1,72 \pm 0,03	1,58 \pm 0,02

Significance of differences in comparison with control group (p): * – p<0.05; ** – p<0.01; *** – p<0.001.

In the blood samples of all patients on the first day there was an increase of activity of catalase which is an enzyme of first line of defense. Catalase is one of the basic enzymes of antioxidant protection and elevation of its activity on the first day after TBI points at activation of lipid peroxidation in patients with MBC. Assessment of dynamic changes has shown gradual decrease of catalase activity which gives evidence of debilitation of proper antioxidant protection.

On the first day in patients with concussion there was insignificant elevation of glutathione as the basic component of protective glutathione system in comparison to the results of control group. However on the third day we observed sharp decline of glutathione level in compared to the original data. The component of glutathione is sulfhydryl (SH) group which plays important role in normal functioning of membrane structures. On the first day after trauma there was mild elevation of SH-groups level but then it was followed by decrease of their level.

In all patients with brain concussion on the first day after trauma we found increase of ceruloplasmin activity as manifestation of defense response. By the third day this level increases almost by 40% in comparison to control group, but then it significantly decreases. It has been proved that ceruloplasmin is the basic antioxidant of blood plasma both in normal and in pathology which prevents and inhibits lipid peroxidation by oxidation of bivalent iron. Antioxidant effect of ceruloplasmin depends on its ferroxidase activity. We can assume that ceruloplasmin takes part in destruction of toxic free radicals of superoxide anion which is a product of aerobic metabolism.

So we can make a conclusion that mobilization of protective antioxidant mechanisms in the brain softens primary activation of lipid peroxidation. However it is

followed by their further exhaustion that leads to destructive changes of nervous cells. That is why early determination, prevention and correction of secondary brain injury largely determine the results of treatment.

Conclusions.

1. In patients with brain concussion activation of free radical oxidation is most pronounced in five days after traumatic brain injury.

2. On the first day of trauma there is expressed activation of protective antioxidant factors (increased activity of catalase, content of ceruloplasmin, SH-groups, glutathione). The dynamic observation has shown gradual decrease of antioxidant activity.

Attention is drawn to the need of the further study of biochemical processes that lead to irreversible changes in nervous tissue, as well as development and implementation of the drugs for correction of energetic metabolism and protection against secondary destruction of the cells.

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